

BRITISH EXPERIENCE IN PREPARING FUTURE POLICE OFFICERS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY

Salohiddinov Nuriddin Fakhridin ugli

Teacher of the Department of Military Training at
the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14644707>

Abstract: This article highlights the experience of the United Kingdom, one of the developed countries, in preparing future police officers for professional activities.

Keywords: police department, vocational education, professional training, police education, constable, inspector, modular system.

In today's era of advancing scientific and technological progress, along with all aspects of our lives, new changes are occurring in the sphere of crime. This necessitates the preparation of personnel in the field of law enforcement, particularly for professional activity, and the improvement of their knowledge, skills, and abilities. For this reason, it is necessary to organize the system of professional education for representatives of this field using modern pedagogical technologies, to carry out the selection, recruitment, and professional training of personnel by utilizing the best practices of developed countries.

There are no unified international standards for the system of initial professional training of students in educational institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. In each country, the procedure for preparing them for professional activity is carried out based on the state's management policy, basic legislation, economic capabilities, as well as national traditions and mentality.

For example, research in this area shows that the procedures for training internal affairs officers for professional activities in countries that separated from the former Soviet Union are practically indistinguishable from each other. A vivid example of this is the following opinion of Russian educators V.A. Sinyanskiy, R.S. Kalenik, and T.P. Afinogenov: "In countries separated from the former Soviet Union, known as the Commonwealth of Independent States, the professional training of police officers is carried out on the basis of the methodology of professional training of police officers of the former Soviet Union"[1].

Russian pedagogical scientist V.V. Zakatov noted that in the United States and European countries, a three-stage system of training police officers for professional activity has been established, and in each country, these stages are implemented in various forms, based on their national educational standards. The first stage is the initial professional training of employees who were first admitted to the police service in regional police departments and educational institutions. At the national level, this stage is equated with general secondary or vocational education. The second stage is the stage of professional training for police officers in various specialties, equivalent to a bachelor's degree in higher education. The third stage is the stage of training managerial personnel for police departments, equivalent to a master's degree in higher education[2].

According to Russian educators N.F. Geyjan, V.V. Balakhonsky, and O.N. Mironkina, the German, French, British, and American models of the system for training police officers for professional activity are among the most advanced in the Western world [3]. Candidates

wishing to serve in the police system of these countries will be selected on a competitive basis.

Among European countries, the UK model of training police officers for professional activities deserves special attention. Today, the British model of training police officers for professional activities is implemented in the following order:

- Initial professional training of employees who were first admitted to the positions of constables of the police service;
- Special professional training for police officers who have expressed a desire to serve in narrow fields of specialization, such as criminal investigation, road patrol service, etc.;
- Training police sergeants and inspectors;
- Training of managerial personnel [4].

In the United Kingdom, the first recruits to the police service undergo training in regional police departments and educational institutions under the "Initial Police Training and Development Programme IPLDP," which includes a two-year period. This programme is the only national programme recognised by all UK police units and was adopted in 2006 [5]. The main objectives of this program are to achieve the following results:

- Introduce the audience to the advantages of serving in police activities;
- Developing students' skills in effective communication with the population;
- Increasing listeners' self-confidence in order to fulfill their assigned service tasks;
- Developing the necessary knowledge and professional competence of trainees to perform service tasks;
- Training trainees to be able to adapt to any conditions of service [6].

The "Initial Program for the Development of Police Training" includes more than 20 disciplines and is implemented in four stages based on a modular system[4]. Each stage concludes with passing test exams. The theoretical part of education is conducted in civil colleges and universities, involving experienced police officers, esteemed professors and teachers, as well as community representatives in the educational process.

In the first stage, called "Introduction to Police Activity," students learn the fundamentals of organizing police work, police strategy, public safety, human rights, first aid, personal safety, and the use of information technology and communication tools in police activities.

In the second stage, "Public Security and Cooperation," they master the basics of crime prevention and operational search activities in the police. They also practice interacting with citizens, cooperating with the population and various social groups, and undergo internships in regional police units to study community issues.

The third stage is considered the main phase of training, also known as "Acquisition of Basic Professional Qualifications by Police Officers." At this stage, students study subjects such as legislation on police activities, fundamentals of police paperwork, criminal investigation, and professional ethics for police officers. After completing this stage, they serve on patrol duty in territorial police units under the mentorship of experienced personnel.

In the fourth stage, "Independent Patrol Service," trainees independently perform patrol duties in territorial police units, relying on their acquired knowledge and skills. During this stage, the head of the regional police department analyzes the trainees' organization and conduct of service, and subsequently submits a recommendation to the educational

institution regarding their suitability for work in the police service. After completing all subjects in the curriculum for initial professional training of police officers, the trainees take final exams and are assigned to constable positions in regional police departments[7].

The experiences of the United States and Britain in implementing initial professional training and continuous education for police officers, as we have mentioned above, are among the most effective examples not only in the West but also among countries worldwide. Having studied the practices of preparing police officers for professional activities in these countries, we can draw the following conclusions:

First, employees serving in all branches of the police force must undergo initial professional training;

Second, there is a strict implementation of a competitive selection system for candidates who express a desire to serve in the police;

Third, newly hired police officers are recruited only after completing initial professional training;

Fourth, the program for initial professional training of police officers is divided into stages based on a modular system, with 25 percent of lessons organized theoretically and the remaining 75 percent practically;

Fifth, almost 50 percent of lessons in the initial professional training program are focused on combat and physical training;

Sixth, one of the distinctive features for obtaining an officer's rank and serving in this position is the requirement of a certain length of service experience in the lower ranks of the police (in the positions of officers and sergeants) and mandatory completion of training according to the corresponding program.

References:

1. Синянский В.А., Каленик Р.С., Афиногенов Т.П. Профессиональная подготовка полицейского в зарубежных странах, передовой опыт, современные технологии. Азимут научных исследований: педагогика и психология. 2020. Т. 9. № 1(30) 153-с.
2. Закатов В.В. Профессиональная подготовка сотрудников полиции за рубежом: особенности и тенденции развития. // Балтийский гуманитарный журнал. 2017. Т. 6. № 4(21) 313-с.
3. Гейжан Н.Ф., Балахонский В.В., Миронкина О.Н. Профессиональный отбор и обучение сотрудников полиции в зарубежных странах. Pedagogical Journal. 2021, Vol. 11, Is. 5A // 503-с.
4. В.В. Закатов. Педагогические особенности первоначальной подготовки полицейских в европейских странах. Труды Академии управления МВД России. 2015. №3 (35). 101 с.
5. Ш.М. Нурадинов, М.Н. Касаткин. Правовые и педагогические особенности реализации права на образование в ходе подготовки кадров для правоохранительных органов Великобритании. Вестник Московского университета МВД России №1 / 2020 г. 28 с.
6. Н.В. Быхтина. Особенности содержания первоначальной подготовки полицейских кадров в России и зарубежных странах. Вестник Восточно-Сибирского Института МВД России 1(84) 2018 г. 156 с.

7. Якубов А.С., Асямов С.В., Таджиев А.А., Миразов Д.М. Полиция зарубежных стран: система организации и опыт профессиональной подготовки кадров: Учебное пособие / – Т.: Издательство «Fan va texnologiya», 2010. – 452 с.

